

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOHAMMED****FIRST NAME: AHMED****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied XUS conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Essay (EUCLID 2024, 7)
2. Starting the Essay (EUCLID 2024, 7)
3. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a paper
4. American VS. British English (EUCLID 2024, 25)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34 - 39)

ACA-401D PERIOD I

1)INTRODUCTION

Since 2020, I have been exploring universities that provide Ph.D. programs through distance or online education. My core area of interest is the development program. After a lot of effort, I came across EUCLID University and found the program that best fits my interests. Then, I immediately communicated with the university and requested information on the accreditation status of its PhD programs. Once I got a satisfactory response, I intensively worked on the mobilization of the financial resources needed for the application and tuition fees. Finally, I applied for the PhD in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (PSDD) program. I was hopeful to be admitted based on the smooth and clear information being provided by Pr. Laurant Cleenewerck and the International Admission Team.

August 14, 2024, is one of the most important days in my life. I received an email message that notified me of my acceptance to the PSDD program. However, I am frank to say that I was worried about how to go ahead with the courses, exams, and papers. Thanks to the EULCID Global Admission, which addressed my worry. It has provided me with email messages, details, and instructions to be sent to me. As I expected, I received the message and detailed instructions that cover the Course Management System (CMS),

Learning Management System (LMS), the goal of the ACA-401D course pack, and the name of the instructor for this opening course, Dr. Kabiru Gulma, among others.

Given my motivation, I complied with the recommended main and immediate actions. Accordingly, I read the initial student orientation, logged in to the CMS, marked it as “started,” logged into the LMS, and accessed the study materials and study instructions for the first course (ACA-401D). My actions have been followed by a warm welcome and congratulations from Dr Kabiru. He has not only confirmed my enrollment in the courses (ACA-401D) but also provided me with a list of his roles that indicated his commitment to providing me with outstanding faculty support. All the guidelines and information provided by Global Admission, Dr. Kabiru, and video tutorials have boosted my morale and confidence in advancing my engagement in the course.

Luckily, I have been working for international organizations for more than 20 years and engaged in planning, monitoring, and reviewing several issues of development-related research, assessments, and design of policy, strategy, program, and project documents. I have full confidence in the value addition of the DSDD program in improving my career performance. Therefore, it is in such spirit that I embarked on reading the ACA-401D course pack of period one.

Accordingly, I thoroughly read the ACA-401D course pack that covers essay writing, punctuation, American VS. British English, plagiarism, a styled guide and its necessity, as well as a sample response paper commented on by the instructor. All these topics have a list of sub-topics with detailed presentations, explanations, and examples for understanding.

Even though the scope of my learning from the ACA-401D course pack is broad, as indicated above, my response paper focuses on six concepts. These concepts are the academic essay, starting the essay, American VS. British English, plagiarism, a style guide, and its necessity.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic Essay is the first concept that I started in my reading of the ACA-401D course pack. It is one of the concepts that covered in Chapter One: Essay Writing. I am informed of the types of academic essays that are dedicated to academic uses. The course pack defines academic essays as “notificational writing produced as part of academic work” (EUCLID 2024, 7). The sample academic writing I am acquainted with includes research findings, reports on empirical fieldwork, books, newspapers, or other periodicals, monographs, conference papers, books or literature reviews, technical reports, and translations.

Based on the reading, I could understand the common writing style followed by most academic essays. This style includes citations and referencing of the authors or the sources and eliciting motivating questions that promote appropriate or further research. In

addition, I realized that the role and aspiration of academic essays, such as responding to hypotheses that share fact-based knowledge or thoughts, are important.

3) STARTING THE ESSAY

This sub-topic has allowed me to learn the basic steps that need to be followed before initiating the essay writing. The steps are flexible and general guidelines that help to produce quality essays. In the first step, I have noted the importance of starting the essay ahead of time, which is consistent with the usual saying that the earlier is, the better. I found the necessity of adequate time to be helpful in reviewing relevant references or literature as well as the chance to examine the information from different angles to identify the ideal topic. As a second step, I am advised to formulate the research question and analyze the activities it entails. Here, I learned the value of looking at the perspectives related to the topic and providing answers to the research question. (EUCLID 2024, 7-8).

For the past 25 years, I have been engaged in project management. Among others, planning is one of the activities of project management. Jointly with the projects team, we used to proactively identify the problem to be addressed, prioritize activities to be executed, resources needed, and how they are executed to achieve the aspired goals. Therefore, I concur with the third step, which insists on the value of a well-prepared essay plan as guidance that indicates not only the information required in relation to the topic but also the research question to be addressed. In particular, I found the figure that presents basic steps in authoring an essay informative. It is complemented by a detailed discussion and explanation that covers researching the topic, organizing the ideas, writing, referencing, editing, and submitting the essay. It is a useful tool for professionals like me who are away from academic writing for a longer time (EUCLID 2024, 7-8).

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPER

I thoroughly went through the list of advice and illustrations made by the rule of thumb for writing papers. It is useful to me as I observed its specific advice on the need to qualify my thesis(hypotheses) at the start. Furthermore, I have understood the need to concentrate on one of the theories being discussed in my course in a way that is aligned with the problem that my thesis work is addressing. In addition, it is strongly recommended that early leading and general statements on an issue related to the thesis be avoided. Another aspect of my takeaway is the value of making my writing attractive to readers. For instance, the rule inspires the use of first person singular while avoiding redundant and passive statements, words, and longer sentences (EUCLID 2024, 12-14).

I am also comfortable with the advice on brief and clear writing as it is worthwhile for my forthcoming paper writing. I will focus on the ideas that I intend to transmit to the target audience. Because it lets the readers pay attention and quickly understand my thoughts, consider my ideas in their work, address a problem, or even critique and debate over it.

Thanks to the rule of thumb that reminded me about plagiarism. I used to comply with the principle of avoiding plagiarism, given my experience with my old employer, the Ethiopian Science and Technology Commission (ETSTC). The ESTC is mandated to promote and educate the role of rewarding innovation and protecting patent rights. In a similar fashion, I consider giving credit to others' paperwork as a reward through quotation and citation while maintaining their genuine message and concept complemented by full referencing. I believe that the authors' research, analysis, and recommendation are executed through a strong commitment to helping global society address social, political, economic, and natural challenges and promote sustainable development.

Therefore, I consider the rule of thumb, "Do not plagiarize," as a code of conduct or ethics that enhances and maintains my professional engagement in the writing of all my papers in DSDS as well as my future career adventure. Otherwise, I have noted the consequence of ignorance of such golden guidance that may lead my work to score poor grades and undermine my morale. To this end, I appreciate the EUCLID University's arrangement of the writing tutors assigned to the course (EUCLID 2024, 12–14). In my forthcoming paper on the DSDD program, I will use the arrangement as required.

5) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I dare to say that I am lucky to have enrolled in the DSDD as it allowed me to learn about American VS. British English, which I have been ignorant of since I started using the language 30 years ago. Their similarity and differences in terms of meaning, spelling, pronunciation, grammar, syntax, punctuation, collective nouns, pluralized adjectives, periods, commas, and quotation marks have enhanced my understanding even more than before. I am also well exposed to the historical factors that contributed to the growth of American English, which is dominant and has a significant influence on "World English" across the world. With this regard, factors such as propulsion size, wealth, economy, progress in higher education, mass media and related technology, culture, and international political and economic position are notable in the growth of American English (EUCLID 2024, 25–26).

Equally, I feel such factors, in addition to military and political power, have a significant contribution in enabling one local language to supersede the other local languages and become the national official language in countries like mine.

I am open to say that I have been confused while using words such as program VS. programme: color VS. colour and center VS. centre. Thanks to the clarification made on this topic, I have noted the root cause of such differences because I am convinced first to decide on the use of either standard American English (SAE) or standard British English (SBE) before I embark on any paper writing (EUCLID 2024, 25–26).

6) PLAGIARISM

I would like to reflect on the rich knowledge and guidance I got on plagiarism and why and how to avoid it through proper citation and referencing. Usually, when I discuss with professionals working in the academic circle, I used to hear the phrase “intellectual robbery.” They use it to indicate when someone’s ideas and words are used in papers but never given credit by the users, therefore never cited and included in the reference list.

The two recommended approaches of in-text citation and listing the work cited are informative. Based on the in-text citation, I am acquainted with the need to put the author’s name and page number of the information in parentheses. I have also noted short quotations and paraphrases among the information to be cited in line with the in-text citation approach. In addition, I am familiar with the citation of longer quotations through no use of quotation marks while indenting them as independent paragraphs. Most importantly, the advice on minimizing the use of quotations and the ideal situation that encourages the use of quotations (EUCLID 2024, 41–42).

The use of paraphrases in my words is the alternative approach that I learned how to use other authors ideas and information in paper writing. I apply the use of different rephrasing while maintaining the precise idea of the author, which is to be complemented by the right citation and referencing the source of information. It is good to mention my understanding of signal phrases, the list of works to be cited, and formats to be complied with when using books, online works, and websites as sources of information, as well as a separate way of footnote refereeing. Lastly, I welcome the three reasons that justify the importance of citing and referencing the source information. I want to suggest one more critical reason to be considered and included if accepted. That is, plagiarism kills innovation and innovative ideas that could be useful to address human problems or needs, as I reflected before (EUCLID 2024, 41–42).

7) STYLE GUIDE

As I pointed out before, I have been engaged in the design, implementation, supervision, and reporting of several development projects of various international and national originations. With little variation, the organizations have developed and used templates for project preparation, budgeting, procurement plans, bid documents, result monitoring frameworks, and reporting. To this end, each one of them has its own specific standard and requirements to be complied with to ensure consistency in relation to content to be followed, information to be included, number of pages, and procedure for quality review and enhancement. Because there are several technical and operational experts involved in the contribution of narrative information, all the team members engaged in the project design will end up with misunderstandings. The projects are approved for funding and implementation once they pass through all these requirements and processes, while those that are never fulfilled will be rejected. In addition, my work in the trade industry sector also enabled me to know the quality and standard of products and services to be complied by the private sector to satisfy the customers’ needs. It is enforced by the

government rules and regulations. Or it is possible to look at the building standards and codes enforced by various countries, such as the need to construct earthquake-resilient buildings. Therefore, I never agree with the argument of creative writers that compromises professionalism.

By the same token, I am glad that the ACA-401D course pack includes a writing style guide. This topic allowed me to know a broad aspect considered in the writing style guide. The application of fonts, manuscript layout, sentence length, structure, spelling, and abbreviations are among the basic aspects that I noted. I have also been exposed to sample sources of knowledge that could be referred to, such as the Economist style guide, the Chicago Manual of Style, and the BBC News style. Importantly, I have observed EUCLID's recommendations in the use of the Chicago Rues (Turabian) and the American English, even though it is flexible to welcome other internationally accepted rules as well as both American and British English. (EUCLID 2024, 41–42).

I welcome these recommended styles and suggested websites for reference as valuable information that helps me to ensure the consistency, quality, and standard of my written papers. So, I feel I am in a better position to fulfill the expectations of the DSDD courses and other readers.

8) CONCLUSION

I dare to say that the ACA-401D course pack has presented comprehensive knowledge that laid a foundation for my forthcoming course papers. The detailed discussion, accompanied by examples, has boosted my quick understanding. Now, I am well exposed to the guidance on essay writing, punctuation, the use of American VS. British English, the importance of avoiding plagiarism, the style guide, and the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). I have also watched the two online videos presented by Professor Gulma. These are the review of sample Response Paper (RP) presentation of copying and pasting information from the improper paper format to the proper ECULID format. In addition, I appreciate EUCLID in including the sample correction made to a response paper. It has enabled me to be aware of how instructors review and provide constructive comments on course papers for improvement.

As I understand the ACA-401D course pack and videos are critically important for the forthcoming ECULID paper and my future professional writings, I am convinced to reread the material and rewatch the videos, including the ones I did not watch.

REFERENCES

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